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4 **Title:** Weighing the Global Built Environment: High Resolution Mapping and Quantification of
5 Material Stocks in Buildings

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53 **Data Availability Statement:** The authors agree with an open and free data policy. Data
54 supporting the findings of this study are available in two supporting information files. The map
55 of material stocks in building will be made available with full spatial (90 m) and thematic (18
56 materials for 5 building types) resolution through the DLR EOC GeoService at
57 <https://geoservice.dlr.de> upon publication of this paper.

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60 **Keywords:** Buildings; Mapping; Earth Observation; Material Stocks; Material Flow Analysis;
61 Industrial Ecology

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63

64 **Abstract**

65 Buildings provide indispensable services for human wellbeing, but their construction and use are
66 responsible for a substantial fraction of societies' resource requirements and greenhouse gas
67 emissions. Mapping and quantifying the material stocks in buildings is a key research frontier in
68 Industrial Ecology. Reliable and spatially highly resolved maps of material stocks in buildings
69 world-wide are so far not available. Existing approaches based on nighttime light data allow
70 large-scale coverage, but their spatial resolution is usually ~0.5-1 km. Other methods using light
71 detection and ranging (LiDAR) and cadaster data achieve higher resolution and accuracy, but do
72 not allow wall-to-wall mapping of large regions. Based on high-resolution Earth Observation
73 data combined with material intensity factors (kg per m³ of building volume), we here quantify
74 and map material stocks in buildings at the unprecedented resolution of 90 m globally. We
75 distinguish 18 types of materials in five types of buildings. We find that global material stocks in
76 buildings amount to 547 (391-672) Gt, approximately half of total global societal material
77 stocks. We find highly unequal distributions of material stocks in buildings per capita and per
78 unit area of each country. Our results agree well with previous detailed estimates of material
79 stocks in buildings in dedicated regions or individual cities. Improved and harmonized material
80 intensity factors emerge as a key research area for improving the accuracy of material stock
81 maps. Our results are available as data products with high spatial and thematic resolution to
82 facilitate future studies; e.g., of secondary resource potentials.

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85 **1. INTRODUCTION**

86 Given the key role of shelter for almost all human activities, buildings are of great importance
87 for provision of decent living conditions (Millward-Hopkins et al., 2020). Provision of housing is
88 a prerequisite for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), as specified in Target
89 11.1 of SDG no. 11. Moreover, buildings are directly or indirectly required for most other SDGs,
90 such as 1, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, or 12, as they enable and provide functions like education, healthcare,

91 nutrition, sanitation, energy supply and other production and consumption activities. Adequate
92 housing is lacking in many parts of the world (Tusting et al., 2019).

93
94 At the same time, construction, maintenance and use of buildings is associated with enormous
95 resource flows (Deetman et al., 2020; Tanikawa et al., 2020; Wiedenhofer et al., 2015) and
96 greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Lamb et al., 2021) as well as other environmental pressures.
97 They are hence of crucial importance for other SDGs such as those related to clean energy and
98 climate action (SDGs 12-13) and responsible production and consumption (SDG11). The extent,
99 spatial patterns and design of buildings strongly co-determine energy requirements for heating,
100 cooling, lighting and transport as well as the related GHG emissions (Creutzig et al., 2016;
101 Haberl et al., 2023) and result in carbon lock-in, determining societal development pathways for
102 decades to come (Seto et al., 2016). Quantifying materials in buildings (Marinova et al., 2020)
103 and mapping their spatial patterns (Haberl et al., 2021; Lanau & Liu, 2020; Peled & Fishman,
104 2021; Schandl et al., 2020; Tanikawa et al., 2020; Tanikawa & Hashimoto, 2009) have emerged
105 as important research areas in Industrial Ecology. Recent progress has been summarized in
106 topical reviews (Fu et al., 2022; Lanau et al., 2019).

107
108 So far, global estimates of socioeconomic material stocks assessed material stocks in all human-
109 made structures. As no explicit breakdowns to specific end-uses respectively types of structures
110 were available, buildings were an unknown part of the total stock. These studies are often at
111 global or regional levels and lack national (and even more so sub-national) resolution. Estimates
112 of total global socioeconomic material stocks derived from data on material flows combined with
113 lifetime estimates have recently become available (Krausmann et al., 2017; Wiedenhofer et al.,
114 2021), with methodological and empirical improvements underway to enable resolving different
115 types of stocks and end-uses, including differentiation of built structures such as buildings, roads
116 and other civil engineering (Streeck 2022a,b, Plank 2022). Several studies have quantified the
117 mass of buildings for specific cities, regions or countries (Gontia et al., 2020; Lanau & Liu,
118 2020; Noll et al., 2022; Schandl et al., 2020; Tanikawa & Hashimoto, 2009; Wiedenhofer et al.,
119 2015), but not for larger areas. One study quantified material stocks in global residential
120 buildings (Marinova et al., 2020), another modelled the quantity of cement and metal stocks in
121 residential buildings (Pauliuk et al., 2021); both these studies are not spatially explicit and were
122 not comprehensive in terms of materials found in buildings.

123
124 Mapping is important, among others because spatial patterns of built structures influence levels
125 of resource use (Haberl et al., 2023). Although not all end-of-life materials can be recycled, maps
126 of built structures can help locating secondary resource potentials (Haberl et al., 2021). As maps
127 of mobility infrastructures are becoming available (Wiedenhofer et al., 2024), building maps can
128 provide complementary data towards that end. Building maps can also help gauging impacts of
129 extreme events or sea-level rise (Symmes et al., 2020). Approaches that quantify material stocks
130 in a spatially-explicit manner have used nighttime lights (Peled & Fishman, 2021; Takahashi et
131 al., 2010), cadaster information (Lanau & Liu, 2020; Tanikawa et al., 2015), big-data approaches
132 (Mao et al., 2020) or remote-sensing light detection and ranging (LiDAR) techniques (Schandl et
133 al., 2020). Nighttime light data allow mapping material stocks in buildings for large regions but
134 can only achieve relatively low spatial resolution (usually >300-750 m). Moreover, these
135 methods have limited capacity to separate material stocks in buildings from those in roads or

136 distinguish building types and suffer from methodological problems such as saturation effects or
137 differences in luminosity between regions. Other data sources such as cadasters or LiDAR are
138 only consistently available for small regions and cannot be used for wall-to-wall mapping of
139 large regions. A combination of optical multi-spectral satellite-borne Earth Observation data for
140 buildings and crowd-sourced data such as Open Street Map (OSM) for roads has been proposed
141 to alleviate that tradeoff, as demonstrated via mapping stocks in Germany and Austria (Haberl et
142 al., 2021) and the USA (Frantz et al., 2023). For buildings, however, a global study of 13,000
143 cities found that OSM is too incomplete for reliable mapping (Q. Zhou et al., 2022). A global,
144 comprehensive and spatially highly resolved map (i.e., at 100 m or less) of material stocks in
145 buildings is yet lacking, to the best of our knowledge.

146

147 Using a global 3D building map derived from Earth Observation data (Esch et al., 2022), our
148 research closes this crucial knowledge gap. The map published by co-authors of this article
149 represents global building volumes and underlying building areas and heights at 90 m spatial
150 resolution. The data therein can be linked with material intensity (MI) factors quantifying the
151 mass of building materials per m^2 or m^3 of building area and volume, respectively (Heeren &
152 Fishman, 2019). We used these data sources to (1) quantify the mass of materials in buildings
153 worldwide, thereby further improving the differentiation of building types, and to (2) map the
154 material stocks in buildings globally at a spatial resolution of 90 m. We assessed the robustness
155 of the results by comparing them with other published material stock estimates and conducted a
156 sensitivity analysis. In Section 3, we analyze the inequality of global distribution of material
157 stocks in buildings per capita and the density of material stocks per each nation's land area, and
158 discuss implications.

159

160

161 **2. METHODS**

162 Most approaches for quantifying and mapping material stocks in buildings proceed by
163 multiplying data on the physical dimensions of buildings, usually floor area [m^2] or building
164 volume [m^3], with suitable material intensity (MI) factors (either [kg/m^2] or [kg/m^3], depending
165 on input data). We here use the volume-based approach developed in previous work for national
166 studies (Frantz et al., 2023; Haberl et al., 2021) and extend it to the global level, thereby
167 harnessing core strengths of the underlying building dataset (Esch et al., 2022).

168

169 **2.1 Building volumes and building type classification**

170 The World Settlement Footprint 3D (WSF3D) is a global dataset quantifying the fraction, total
171 area, average height and total volume of buildings for a grid with 90 m cell size (Esch et al.,
172 2022). It was generated using a modified version of the World Settlement Footprint 2019
173 (WSF2019) human settlements mask (Marconcini et al., 2021) derived from Sentinel-1 and
174 Sentinel-2 satellite data at 10 m spatial resolution in combination with 12 m digital elevation data
175 derived by radar imagery collected by the TanDEM-X mission. The WSF3D refers to the year
176 2019. Due to data security regulations, the original geometric resolution of 12 m for the building
177 height and volume estimations was finally spatially aggregated to a 90 m gridding to allow for an
178 open and free distribution.

179

180 As reported in Esch et al. (2022), the original WSF3D exhibits a systematic underestimation of
 181 the heights of high-rise buildings (>50 m). For this study, we therefore created an enhanced
 182 version WSF3Dv2, where local height information for a total of 711,448 skyscrapers and high-
 183 rise buildings provided by the Emporis database (Emporis, 2022) was integrated (Section 2 of
 184 Supplementary Information S1). A new validation based on the reference sites already used by
 185 Esch et al. (2022) documents that the average height estimation error of -2.3 m in the WSF3D
 186 could now be reduced to -0.22 m for the new WSF3Dv2 (Section 2.3 and Table S6 in
 187 Supplementary Information S1).

188
 189 Based on the information provided by the building height layer of the improved WSF3Dv2, we
 190 then implemented a new approach towards the classification of five building types using a
 191 threshold-driven categorization (Table 1). All buildings <3m height were classified as
 192 lightweight. A height threshold of 12m was used to distinguish single-family and multifamily
 193 houses for buildings of intermediate height (3-50m). The outcome of this classification was a
 194 map assigning the dominant building type per 90 m grid cell. The separation between residential
 195 and non-residential use was applied to all buildings using the GHS-BUILT-S R2023A (JRC,
 196 2022) dataset. The defined classes and the underlying threshold settings are listed in Table 1.
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Table 1. Building types and related thresholds classified on the basis of the WSF3Dv2 data.

Class ID	Building type	WSF3Dv2 Building Height [m]	GHS-BUILT-S [class]
LW	Lightweight	< 3	residential + non-residential
RS	Residential single-family house (residential single)	3-12	residential
RM	Residential multi-family house (residential multi)	12-50	residential
NR	Non-residential	3-50	Non-residential
HR	High-rise	50-100	residential + non-residential

200
 201
 202 **2.2 Material intensity factors**
 203 We compiled and quality-controlled material intensity factors from recent literature, in particular
 204 from data compilations (Heeren & Fishman, 2019; Li et al., 2023), reviews (Lanau et al., 2019)
 205 and datasets developed for own previous studies (Baumgart et al., 2022; Frantz et al., 2023;
 206 Haberl et al., 2021) to assemble a globally representative set of MI factors used for this study
 207 (Supplementary Information S1).
 208

209 One difficulty is that some countries or regions are very well covered in the literature, while few,
 210 if any, studies exist for others. Furthermore, varying building definitions and scopes of the
 211 underlying studies make extensive harmonization and quality control necessary. We therefore
 212 decided for the following regional subdivision: We developed specific MI factors for three large
 213 countries/regions with good data availability: North America (USA and Canada), China, and
 214 Japan. For North America, we used a detailed MI dataset developed for a separate project
 215 covering the conterminous United States of America (Frantz et al., 2023) based on a large
 216 number of studies for most building categories used here. For China, we relied on a recent
 217 compilation of MI factors for non-residential and multifamily residential buildings (Li et al.,
 218 2023), complemented by additional literature for building types not covered in that dataset

219 (Supplementary Information S1). Japan’s building stock has very specific characteristics and is
220 well researched (Tanikawa et al., 2014; Tanikawa & Hashimoto, 2009), hence we developed a
221 specific dataset despite the low number of available studies. For other OECD countries, averages
222 of available data points were used. For all other regions, we used global averages that we deemed
223 more reliable than the available studies, mostly because their quality and comprehensiveness
224 varied substantially and it was unclear how representative the individual studies were for the
225 entire region. For lightweight and high-rise buildings, we used global averages for all regions
226 except USA/Canada due to lacking region-specific data. Detailed information is available in
227 Supplementary Information S1 (Tables S4 and S5).

228
229 Our MI dataset distinguishes five building types: residential single-family house (abbreviated
230 residential single), residential multi-family house (abbreviated residential multi), non-residential,
231 lightweight, high-rise; the latter two building categories can be either residential or non-
232 residential (Table S4 in Supplementary Information S1). We use MI factors for 18 individual
233 materials clustered in four groups: (1) metals (iron/steel, copper, aluminum, other metals), (2)
234 biomass (timber, other biomass), (3) mineral materials (concrete, aggregates not used in
235 concrete, clay bricks, mortar, gypsum, ceramics, glass, other minerals), (4) fossil-fuel based and
236 other materials (bitumen, plastics), and (5) other materials not directly attributable to either
237 category (e.g., undefined insulation, paint). Table S4 in Supplementary Information S1 reports
238 the sources of the MI factors used in the calculations; all factors used in the calculations are
239 reported in Table S5 in the Supplementary Information S1. We used the same MI factors for
240 USA and Canada because buildings are similar in these countries, hence case studies from both
241 countries were used to generate the factors used in our analysis (while Canada is part of “Other
242 OECD” in summary tables later on). For EU-27 (shown separately in the results section), we
243 used the MI factors for “Other OECD”.

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245

246 **2.3 Uncertainty analysis**

247 We assessed the robustness of our approach by comparing our material stock estimates with
248 results from other available literature on global material stocks in buildings (Marinova et al.,
249 2020; Pauliuk et al., 2021) as well as 16 regional or city-level cases for which we were able to
250 obtain or reconstruct their respective regional boundaries. To explore the influence of the
251 variability of MI factors on stock estimates, we conducted a sensitivity analysis (Saltelli et al.,
252 2000). A systematic quantification of uncertainties (e.g., through Monte-Carlo analysis) was out
253 of scope due to data limitations, in particular regarding material intensities of buildings, as well
254 as the novel interdisciplinary combination of multiple methods, data streams and domain
255 expertise needed for this study.

256

257 Because the uncertainty of the building map was previously discussed (Esch et al., 2022), we
258 here focused on the uncertainty of the MI factors. For all regions and building types where a
259 sufficient number of estimates (more than ~10, except for Japan, see above) was available, we
260 calculated the interquartile range of all MI factors and used the 25th and 75th percentile as lower
261 respectively upper bound MI factor in addition to the average. For the other regions we derived
262 ranges in the same manner from the global total of all regions and building types. For details see
263 Supplementary Information S1.

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3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mass of material stocks in global buildings

We found that the mass of all material stocks in buildings worldwide in the year 2019 amounted to 547 Gt, with a minimum estimate of 391 Gt and a maximum of 672 Gt (Table 2). The ‘best guess’ amounts to 53 % of the total mass of socioeconomic material stocks of 1,033 Gt \pm 8 % in 2015 (Wiedenhofer et al., 2021). A third of the building stock is located in China, 15 % in the EU-27, 11 % in Other Asia and 10 % in the Middle East and Africa; building stocks in all other regions are <10 % each. 89 % of all material stocks in buildings are minerals (a broad group of materials that includes aggregates, concrete, bricks, glass and other materials). Metals amount to 5.4 %, most of which is iron/steel, but aluminum, copper and other metals also play important roles. Biomass – mostly wood – contributes 4.0 % to the total. Fossil-fuel based materials such as plastics and bitumen as well as other materials such as insulation or paint play a relatively minor role.

Globally, residential single-family houses (‘residential, single’) are the most important building type (60 %), although this differs widely between regions (see Table 2 and Figure 4a).

Residential multi-family houses (‘residential, multi’) are the second-most important category (27 %), while the others play a minor role. It should be noted, however, that the distinction of residential and non-residential buildings using satellite-based Earth observation data carries substantial uncertainty. This partly results from mixed uses within the same building which frequently occur in multi-family buildings in many cities that cannot be recognized from space. The data shown in Table 2 for the global total are reported in Supporting Information S2 for all countries and with full resolution of material types.

292 Table 2. Mass of materials in the global building stock in the year 2019, breakdown by groups of
 293 materials and building types for ‘best guess’ MI factors [Gt]. Note that the global total may
 294 slightly differ from the sum of regions due to rounding.

	Global	China	EU-27	FSU	Japan	LAM	MAF	Other Asia	Other OECD	USA
Total material stocks										
* Minimum	391.0	161.2	52.8	23.4	9.7	19.8	34.3	39.1	19.3	31.4
* ‘Best guess’	547.3	200.4	80.7	34.8	10.3	31.1	53.4	60.8	29.5	46.3
* Maximum	671.6	240.7	99.3	43.9	11.2	39.7	68.4	77.5	36.0	54.9
Breakdown by groups of materials										
* Metals	29.3	6.2	3.8	2.9	0.7	2.4	5.4	4.8	1.6	1.4
* Minerals	484.8	190.3	70.6	29.3	9.7	26.2	43.8	51.3	25.4	39.1
* Biomass	21.8	3.8	3.5	1.6	0.6	1.6	2.6	3.0	1.5	3.6
* Fossil/other	11.4	0.1	2.7	1.0	0.2	0.9	1.5	1.8	1.0	2.2
Breakdown by building types										
Residential, single	326.6	106.4	49.0	18.5	3.0	22.3	36.4	41.6	18.4	30.9
Residential, multi	147.0	79.5	17.8	9.9	5.9	4.0	7.5	9.6	5.8	7.0
Non-residential	32.7	6.7	10.4	2.3	0.5	1.2	1.2	2.1	3.2	5.1
Lightweight	37.9	7.2	3.3	3.7	0.8	3.2	8.2	6.5	1.9	3.1
High-rise	3.2	0.6	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	1.0	0.2	0.2

295 Note: country/region abbreviations: USA United States of America, EU-27 European Union (27 countries), Other OECD: Other
 296 countries belonging to the Organization of Economic Co-Operation and Development (excluding Japan, USA and EU-27), ASIA
 297 Other Asia (excluding China), FSU Former Soviet Union, LAM Latin and Middle America, MAF Middle East and Africa. Gt ...
 298 Gigatons (1 Gt = 10⁹ t = 1 Pg = 10¹⁵ g = 1 billion metric tons).

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 300
 301 Comparisons with previous studies show similarities as well as differences. In Table S8 in
 302 Supplement S1 we report our global building stock estimates along with those of Marinova et al.
 303 (2020). Overall, our estimate for material stocks in residential buildings is almost one-third lower
 304 than that found by Marinova et al. (2020); even our estimate for all buildings is a bit (11 %)
 305 lower. Because the distinction between residential and non-residential buildings in our study is
 306 not very robust, it is at present not clear which of these two comparisons is more meaningful.
 307 The built-up mass of six material categories (concrete, iron/steel, timber, aluminum, copper, and
 308 glass) found in the two studies is also reported in Table S8.

309
 310 Comparison with results of Pauliuk et al. (2021) are not straightforward because they report
 311 cement, not concrete, and also refer only to residential buildings. When we extrapolate Pauliuk et
 312 al.’s cement results assuming that cement has an average share of 11% in concrete (Portland
 313 Cement Association, 2023), their result implies a global total of 127 Gt of concrete in residential
 314 buildings, which compares well with our result for residential buildings (126 Gt), in particular
 315 considering possible inaccuracies in distinguishing residential from non-residential buildings.
 316 When adding up aggregates and cement in Pauliuk et al.’s study (which – in contrast to ours – do
 317 not include aggregates used for other purposes than making concrete), we get 106 Gt, 16% lower
 318 than our result. For timber, Pauliuk et al. report 16 Gt (our result for residential buildings is 19
 319 Gt) and for steel 6 Gt (our result: 8 Gt).

320

321 Differences emerge from two categories of input data used in calculations: (1) the inventory of
322 housing stocks, and (2) the material intensity (MI) values. We here utilized remotely-sensed
323 estimates of building volumes, whereas both Marinova et al. (2020) and Pauliuk et al. (2021)
324 used outcomes of Integrated Assessment Models. Databases used to derive MI factors also differ.
325 We here considered 587 MI factors drawn from 93 studies. Just as Pauliuk et al. and Marinova et
326 al., we used MI factors derived from the literature. All three studies used mostly (but not
327 entirely) the same primary sources; we added some that had not been available in the earlier
328 work. Furthermore, MI factors were derived differently. Individual MI data points had to be
329 aggregated, which introduces further differences: studies used different numbers of regions as
330 well as varying numbers and definitions of building types to best suit their methods to calculate
331 building volumes. Some study-specific assumptions and different procedures in deriving means
332 may cause further variation. These considerations imply that this research field is still in flux,
333 and further harmonization and data collection will be required to derive more robust results.
334

335 **3.2 Global patterns of material stocks in buildings**

336 Figure 1 shows the global distribution of material stocks in buildings. The map has a spatial
337 resolution of 90 m and, for each pixel, contains data on the mass of 18 materials in five
338 categories of buildings (see lower part of Table 2; full resolution in terms of materials in
339 Supplementary Information S2). The map is available DLR data product at
340 <https://geoservice.dlr.de> (*upon publication of this paper*).
341

342
343 Figure 1. Global high-resolution map of the mass of materials in buildings. This global map
344 displays values of 'kt per pixel' aggregated over larger regions for visualization purposes. Values
345 for individual pixels (of approximately 8,200 m² at the equator) cannot be displayed at global
346 scale. 222 kt is the global maximum for a single pixel. The image uses a Standard Deviation
347 stretch of 2 to increase the visibility of higher values. Data behind this map are available at full
348 spatial and temporal resolution as DLR data product at <https://geoservice.dlr.de> (upon
349 publication of the paper).

350
351 In Figure 2 we show examples for eight cities, one per region, demonstrating the amount of
352 spatial detail present (but scarcely visible) in the global map. The 'height' in the pseudo-3D
353 maps in the outtakes indicates the mass of buildings per 90 m pixel.
354

355
 356 Figure 2. Maps of material stocks in buildings in eight selected cities (one per region) around the
 357 world. The squares delimiting the 3D outtakes measure 5x5 km. Due to the projection used, the
 358 size of pixels differs between cities: At the equator, they measure 90x90 m, but their exact size
 359 varies according to the location of each city in relation to the equator. Data behind this map are
 360 available at full spatial and temporal resolution as DLR data product at <https://geoservice.dlr.de>
 361 (*upon publication of the paper*).
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 363

364 With a resolution of 90 m, our results are substantially more fine-grained than a previous global
 365 analysis that quantified building volumes at 500 m resolution (Y. Zhou et al., 2022). Moreover,
 366 we present a global wall-to-wall data product covering material stocks in buildings, while the

367 Zhou et al. dataset is restricted to building volumes in selected urban areas. In addition, Zhou et
 368 al. modeled building volumes indirectly from Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) backscatter
 369 intensity, instead of deriving height differences from a high-resolution digital elevation model
 370 (as done in the case of the WSF3D processing).

371
 372 Our results reveal substantial global differences between countries in terms of material stocks in
 373 buildings per capita and per km² of each country's territory (here denoted as 'land area'; see
 374 Figure 3). The share of building types in total building material stocks per region differ
 375 substantially. High-rise buildings play a minor role everywhere. The share of lightweight
 376 buildings differs substantially, and is lowest in China and highest in Middle East and Africa.
 377 Residential single-family buildings play a small role in Japan, most likely due to its high
 378 population density and limited land availability for settlements. Moreover, the mass of single-
 379 family houses in Japan is small due to the prevalence of wooden buildings with low material
 380 intensity. In several other regions, roughly two-thirds of the mass of buildings is in residential
 381 single-family houses (EU-27, Latin and Middle America, Middle East and Africa, Other Asia,
 382 Other OECD). Residential multi-family houses play a large role in China and Japan, while their
 383 mass is comparatively small in Latin and Middle America and Middle East and Africa.
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385
 386 Figure 3. Global distribution and inequality of materials in buildings. (a) Distribution of total
 387 material stocks to building types per region. (b) Total material stocks in buildings per capita in
 388 each country [t/cap]. (c) Total material stocks in buildings per unit land area of each country's
 389 territory [kt/km²], (d) Material stocks in buildings per unit of GDP in purchasing-power-parities
 390 (GDP_{ppp}) [kg/\$]. Data behind this Figure are available in Supporting Information S2.

391
392 Income can partially explain these patterns (Table 3a), in line with previous analyses (Schiller &
393 Roscher, 2023). Per-capita stocks in high-income countries are 6.6 times larger than those in
394 low-income countries, the inequality in available building volume per capita (m^3/cap) is almost
395 as large (factor 5.5). Income inequalities reported in World Bank data are even larger (factor 28),
396 and stocks per unit GDP differ substantially as well. This also implies (last column) that building
397 mass per unit of GDP is lower in the high-income group than in low-income countries. This
398 tendency towards lower stock values per unit of GDP in high-income countries needs further
399 scrutiny; it could result from tendencies towards stock saturation in higher-income regions
400 (Wiedenhofer et al., 2021). The mass of buildings per unit GDP differs considerably between
401 regions and countries as well (Figure 3d, Table 3b). Note that these differences should not be
402 overinterpreted, in particular in regions where economic activities outside formal markets (not or
403 only partially reflected in GDP) play an important role.

404
405
406 Table 3. Indicators showing differences respectively inequalities between regions in terms of total material stocks in
407 buildings, stocks per capita and land area, building volume per capita, population density and Gross Domestic
408 Product in purchasing power parities (GDP_{ppp}) per capita as well as stocks per unit of GDP

	Total stocks [Mt]	Stocks per capita [t/cap]	Stocks per land area [kt/km ²]	Building volume per capita [m ³ /cap]	Population density [cap/km ²]	GDP _{ppp} per capita [US\$/cap]	Stocks per unit GDP _{ppp} [kg/US\$]
(a) Breakdown by income groups							
High income	172 794	140	4.79	453	34	51 396	2.72
Upper middle income	290 899	103	4.99	244	49	17 397	5.91
Lower middle income	68 994	24	3.13	86	132	7 030	3.37
Low income	14 223	21	0.92	83	43	1 817	11.76
(b) Breakdown by regions							
China	200 430	146	21.45	278	147	17 067	8.55
EU-27	80 733	183	19.83	532	108	47 906	3.82
FSU	34 792	119	1.59	406	13	21 909	5.45
Japan	10 270	81	27.49	326	338	42 394	1.92
LAM	31 072	48	1.52	171	32	15 455	3.12
MAF	53 417	34	1.53	126	45	7 920	4.32
Other Asia	60 837	23	5.24	82	226	9 068	2.56
Other OECD	29 450	115	1.35	357	12	41 242	2.78
USA	46 278	141	4.88	518	35	65 120	2.16

409
410
411 In terms of regional patterns (Table 3b), we found the highest building volumes per capita in the
412 EU-27 and the USA, lowest in Other Asia. Per unit area, material stocks are highest in Japan,
413 which is plausible given its very high population density; values for China and the EU-27 are
414 only slightly lower, despite their substantially lower population density. This results from higher
415 per-capita material stocks and building volumes in these regions. Material stocks per unit GDP

416 are lowest in Japan, followed closely by the USA. This may result from the prevalence of timber
417 in buildings and the larger role of lightweight buildings, as well as the high importance of the
418 tertiary sector in these regions. Chinas material stocks per capita already exceed the average
419 value of the group of high-income countries, despite being classified as an upper middle-income
420 country and despite its lower building volume per capita. This may result from the prevalence of
421 concrete buildings in China, reflected in relatively high MI factors reported in the recent data
422 compilation (Li et al., 2023) upon which our work relies. Note that we can offer only speculative
423 conjectures, as explaining these patterns would require additional analyses beyond the scope of
424 this paper.

425
426 At the country level, per-capita inequalities of material stocks in buildings are substantial and
427 range from less than 10 tons/capita in some Least-Developed Countries to >300 tons/capita in
428 Finland, the Vatican and the Christmas Islands. Building volumes available per person range
429 from <10 m³/cap to >500 m³/cap; i.e., vary by a factor of > 50 (Supplementary Information S2).
430 These patterns are analyzed in Figure 4 that displays Lorenz curves for building volume and
431 material stocks in buildings per capita as well as GDP per capita. We found that the inequality of
432 building volumes per capita is slightly smaller (Gini coefficient 0.41) than that of material stocks
433 (0.45), which is slightly smaller than the inequality in per-capita GDP_{ppp}. Because population
434 density can be assumed to influence building volumes per capita, we also depict per-capita land
435 area (the inverse of population density) in Figure 4. Per-capita land area is still more unequally
436 distributed, reflecting the large global differences in population density. Inequality in material
437 stocks and volume of buildings rather resembles GDP inequalities than differences in population
438 density.

439

440
 441 Figure 4. Lorenz curves representing the inequality in global country-level per-capita values of
 442 GDPppp, building volume and material stocks in buildings. The more a curve deviates from the
 443 dashed 45° line, and the larger the Gini index, the larger the inequality. Data behind this Figure
 444 are available in Supporting Information S2.

445
 446
 447 **3.3. Data quality and sensitivity**
 448 Our material stock results hinge on the accuracy of (1) quantification of building volumes and
 449 (2) material intensity (MI) factors. Building volume data were validated in the underlying
 450 remote-sensing study (Esch et al., 2022). In order to gauge the effect of MI factors, we conducted
 451 a sensitivity analysis.

452
 453 The results of the sensitivity analysis (minimum/maximum values compared to ‘Best guess’
 454 estimates obtained by varying the MI factors) are presented in Figure 5a for the 20 countries with
 455 the largest total material stocks in buildings. Minimum and maximum values differ from the
 456 ‘Best guess’ result by between one-quarter and one-third, depending on the data quality in the
 457 respective region; e.g., in terms of availability and consistency of data to derive MI factors. Full
 458 information on the sensitivity for all countries and building types is available in Supporting
 459 Information S2.

460
 461 Our validation and sensitivity analysis suggest that our results are useful as first comprehensive
 462 database with global coverage and high spatial resolution, but they also reveal limitations

463 requiring future work. The large spread of overall results emerging from the sensitivity analysis
464 (Figure 5a) suggests that more primary research to determine MI factors is required to obtain
465 more accurate results, in particular for regions where they are currently absent or very scarce,
466 and where our sensitivity analysis most likely underestimates uncertainties.

467
468 Figure 5b compares snippets from our global map with 16 individual results for 14 sub-national
469 regions, mostly cities, from 13 independent studies (for detail see Supporting Information S2).
470 The number of results is larger than the number of cities because for one city (Vienna, Austria),
471 three different results were available. Material stocks found in the independent studies range
472 from 53 % (Gothenburg, Sweden) to 200 % (Samothrace, Greece) of our results, but reasonable
473 agreement is found for most cities/studies. Generally, our results compare to other studies within
474 the range suggested by our uncertainty estimate. Deviations are up- and downwards; that is, they
475 show that there are uncertainties, but do not indicate a bias. Larger deviations were found for
476 older studies (Kleemann et al., 2017), for very specific locations like the Greek island
477 Samothrace (Noll et al., 2022) and Gothenburg, Sweden (Gontia et al., 2020). The latter two
478 cases have untypical building styles not captured in our region-averaged MI factors due to a
479 prevalence of traditional stone buildings in Samothrace and of wood buildings in Gothenburg
480 that also showed in other mapping exercises (Peled & Fishman, 2021). Deviations for Chiclayo
481 (Mesta et al., 2019) and Antigua and Barbuda (Bradshaw et al., 2020) affect data-scarce regions
482 for which we had to rely on global-average MI factors due to lacking regional MI datasets. While
483 our results are well in line with other Chinese regions (Liang et al., 2023), we find substantial
484 deviations for Beijing (Mao et al., 2020) that may, among other aspects, have to do with
485 deviations in coverage that cannot be excluded with respect to our reconstruction of the boundary
486 shape file (more detail in Supporting Information S1). In general, global results are expected to
487 deviate from local case studies because global or regional factors cannot capture all local
488 context-specific conditions (Schiller et al., 2019).

489
490 For some of these problems, research is under way that should allow narrowing the ranges in the
491 foreseeable future. Construction technologies, and with them the material composition of
492 buildings, as well as the mass of materials required per m² of floor space and per m³ of building
493 volume, differ between countries or regions. In large countries, they may even differ between
494 regions, and of course change over time. Efforts to harmonize building definitions and
495 improvements of factors to convert area-based to volume-based material intensity factors
496 (Section 1.2 and Table S2 in Supporting Information S1) would be helpful. At present, most
497 empirical research into the material intensity of buildings is carried out in Europe, North
498 America and Japan, while few studies are available for other regions (Supplementary
499 Information S1). Improved regional coverage will allow more robust quantifications and
500 mappings. Better MI factor databases would be a precondition for improving these results and
501 would allow a systematic assessment of uncertainties; e.g., using Monte-Carlo approaches.
502 Building age is another important factor that could not be considered here, but improved models
503 that infer building age from urban form indicators are gradually becoming available (Nachtigall
504 et al., 2023); inclusion of such data respectively model outcomes could help improving future
505 maps. In June 2023, which was too late to be included in this work, the Joint Research Centre
506 (JRC) released a new GHSL 2023 version; integrating these data for building type separation
507 could help further improving our results.

508

509 (a)

510

511 (b)

512

513 Figure 5. Sensitivity analysis and comparison with previous local/regional studies. (a) Results of

514 the sensitivity analysis for MI factors obtained with 25/75 percentiles for the 20 countries with

515 highest absolute material stock amounts. Sensitivity of the results to changes in MI factors is

516 represented as error bars. The primary (left) axis shows results in absolute numbers, the

517 secondary (right) axis as per-cent of the “best guess” result for each region. (b) Comparison of

518 our results from our global mapping exercise (100%) with results of case studies for specific

519 cities and regions. See Supplementary Information S1 for detail. References: (Bradshaw et al.,

520 2020; Gontia et al., 2019; Haberl et al., 2021; Kleemann et al., 2017; Lanau & Liu, 2020;

521 Lederer et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2023; Mao et al., 2020; Miatto et al., 2019; Mollaei et al., 2021;

522 Noll et al., 2022; Stephan & Athanassiadis, 2018). Data behind this Figure are available in

523 Supporting Information S2.

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4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Buildings contain about two thirds of all socioeconomic material stocks, which includes substantial fractions of energy- and emission-intensive materials such as concrete and metals. Global material stocks in buildings amount to 547 Gt in the year 2019, which is ~72 t/cap. Inequalities in per-capita stocks and building volumes are substantial. Our results represent progress in terms of spatial resolution and are based on state-of-the art methods, but substantial uncertainties prevail for world regions with scarce data as well as for important differentiations such as that between residential and other buildings. More accurate quantifications and maps will require additional work, among others better harmonization of building definitions and more empirical studies of the material intensity of buildings.

The data discussed in this article are freely available through the DLR EOC GeoService (<https://geoservice.dlr.de>). They open a host of future research avenues. For example, they can be used to calculate resources (materials and energy) and emissions (e.g., GHG emissions) ‘embodied’ in current building stock using recently developed methods (Kennedy, 2020; Stephan & Athanassiadis, 2017; Vélez-Henao & Pauliuk, 2023). Our results can contribute to future analyses of the role of material stocks and their spatial patterns as co-determinants of energy use, material flows or GHG emissions (Duro et al., 2024; Haberl et al., 2023). They can help localizing secondary resource potentials (Marinova et al., 2020), calculating future waste flows (Streck et al., 2020, 2021) and analyzing lock-in effects (Seto et al., 2016). Analyses of the patterns presented above, in particular of the inequalities in building volumes and material stocks per capita in the context of the Sustainable Development Goals, also emerge as worthwhile endeavors.

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804 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

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Supporting Information

Supporting information is linked to this article on the *JIE* website:

Supporting Information S1: This supporting information data file provides additional text and tables on methods.

Supporting Information S2: This supporting information data file provides additional results at national-level resolution.

806 807 **DATA PRODUCT LINKED TO THIS ARTICLE**

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809 The map of material stocks in building will be made available with full spatial (90 m) and
810 thematic (18 materials for 5 building types) resolution through the DLR EOC GeoService at
811 <https://geoservice.dlr.de> upon publication of this paper.
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